

An *In-silico* attempt to catch hold of the novel microRNAs in the Bio Energy Plant (*Jatropha curcus*): A Big Search

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ABSTRACT

The oil-rich and weedy plant *Jatropha* has been hailed as the most promising source of biofuel on the planet, as a non-food, drought-resistant and oil-rich crop, *Jatropha curcas* fulfils many of the requirements for biofuel industries.

A better understanding of the biochemical pathway leading to the synthesis of *Jatropha* oil and its regulation both by exogenous and endogenous factors is essential for facilitating increased yield. Increasing evidence has shown that miRNAs play multiple roles in various biological processes. The research finds previously known miRNAs from various plant species expressed sequence tags (EST) database to search for potential miRNAs and their targets in *Jatropha curcus*.

Here we present an EST (Expressed Sequence Tags) based homology search approach for the detection of miRNAs and their targets in *Jatropha curcas* using previously known miRNA sequences from *Oryza sativa*, *Arabidopsis thaliana*, *Populus trichocarpa*, *Ricinus communis*, *Citrus sinensis*, *Vitis vinifera*. We find presence of no miRNAs. What can be the cause?

Introduction:

Earlier Science revolved around proteins, considering them as the sole regulatory molecules of the genome¹. Till then a lot of work was carried out to understand the regulatory mechanisms of eukaryotic gene expressions. The first landmark in the field of gene silencing and small RNAs was made in 1990's. It all started when a strange form of gene regulation was described that involved the binding of one RNA molecule to another. Then a few years back, with reports that there are hundreds of small RNAs in the genome²⁻⁵, it came into view.

There was the possibility that a whole layer of gene regulation involving very small RNA molecules called microRNAs had been overlooked for 40 years. But still there were doubts as to the importance of microRNAs — the wave might yet turn out to be scarcely a ripple, let alone a tsunami. With the description by Palatnik et al. of the role of microRNAs in controlling plant development, and other new publications reporting important functions in animals, the wave looks very real — and big⁶⁻⁹.

In 1993, while studying mutations that changed the timing of developmental events in the worm *Caenorhabditis elegans*, Victor Ambros made a startling discovery¹⁰. A mutation that caused an increase in the translation of RNA to protein was found to be in a second, very small RNA molecule. The small RNA was shown to bind through base pairing to one end of an RNA that controlled the worm's ability to develop properly. The binding of the small RNA resulted in a block to translation of the messenger RNA. Seven years later, a second case of a small RNA used to regulate the translation of a messenger RNA was reported¹¹.

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The next task was to determine what these microRNAs were doing. Recently, two groups published the dramatic findings that many of the apparent targets of plant microRNAs are transcription factors implicated in the control of developmental processes^{2,4}. Transcription factors are proteins that control gene activity. So the findings led to speculation that a primary role for microRNAs in plants is to regulate gene expression after a cell division event that leads to the formation of two different cell types.

MiRNA attaches to a piece of messenger RNA (mRNA) – which is the master template for building a protein – in a non-coding part at one end of the molecule. This acts as a signal to prevent translation of the mRNA into a protein.

Over 4000 miRNAs have been discovered in all studied eukaryotes including mammals, fungi and plants. More than 700 miRNAs have so far been identified in humans and over 800 more are predicted to exist.

Comparing miRNAs between species can even be used to delineate molecular evolutionary history on the basis that the complexity of an organism's phenotype may reflect that of the microRNA found in the genotype.

With the development of computational methods, several computer software programs have been developed to help to identify plant potential miRNA target genes in mRNA sequences. Because almost all miRNAs show perfect or near-perfect complementarity with their targets in plants, it is much easier to predict miRNA targets using a BLAST search of mRNA database for plants. More and more studies have shown this is a powerful approach that has been used to successfully select potential miRNA targets in mRNA sequences for experimental validation¹².

Due to their abundant presence and far-reaching potential, miRNAs have all sorts of functions in physiology, from cell differentiation, proliferation, apoptosis to the endocrine system, haematopoiesis, fat metabolism, limb morphogenesis. They display different expression profiles from tissue to tissue, reflecting the diversity in cellular phenotypes and as such suggest a role in tissue differentiation and maintenance.

Material and Methods:

Databases of miRNAs, EST, and mRNA sequences:

To search potential miRNAs, a total of previously known 1392 miRNAs and their precursor sequences from *Oryza sativa*, *Arabidopsis thaliana*, *Populus trichocarpa*, *Ricinus communis*, *Citrus sinensis*, *Vitis vinifera* were obtained from miRNA Registry Database (Release 18.0, November 2011; <http://www.mirbase.org>)¹¹. These miRNAs were defined as a reference set of miRNA sequences. The reason we choose them as reference miRNAs is because of a few assays identified miRNAs in them and are deposited in publicly available databases. We have referred to the previous work on computational prediction of microRNAs by Zhang et al.¹⁴. To avoid the redundant or overlapping miRNAs, the repeated sequences of miRNAs within the above species were removed and the remaining sequences were used as query sequences for BLAST search. *J. curcus* expressed sequence tag (EST) and mRNA databases were obtained from the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) Gen-Bank nucleotide databases (<http://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>).

Availability of software:

Comparative software BLAST-2.2.14 was used from NCBI GenBank. MFold 3.1 from web-side (<http://www.bioinfo.rpi.edu/applications/mfold/rna/form1.cgi>) was used on line to analyze secondary structure of RNAs. MirEval (<http://tagc.univ-mrs.fr/mireval>) was used for miRNA precursor prediction¹⁵. BLASTX from NCBI (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>) was used for analysis of potential targets.

Prediction of miRNA:

Procedure of search for potential miRNAs in *J. curcus* was showed in Fig. 1. This method used in the study was described by Zhang and co-workers with some modifications. Briefly, the previously known miRNAs were screened out, and the redundant sequences were removed. The remaining miRNA sequences were subjected to BLAST search for *J. curcus* miRNA homologs against EST databases.

The mature sequences of all miRNAs were subjected to BLASTn search in the *J. curcus* EST databases using BLASTn 2.2.9. These Adjusted BLASTn parameter settings were as follows: expect values were set at 1000; low complexity was chosen as the sequence filter; the number of descriptions and alignments was raised to 1,000. The default word-match size between the query and database sequences was seven. RNA sequences were considered miRNA candidates only if they fit the following criteria: (1) at least 18 nt length were adopted between the predicted mature miRNAs and (2) allowed to have 0-5 nt mismatches in sequence with all previously known plant mature miRNAs¹⁴. In the cited reference the miRNA of cotton plant was predicted and having 5 mismatches for two family of miRNA, miR-403 and miR-407. The ESTs that closely matched the previously known plant mature miRNAs were included in the set of miRNA candidates and used for additional characterization based on the following criteria: (1) the entire EST sequence was selected to predict the secondary structures and to screen for miRNA precursor sequences; (2) the selected ESTs were further compared with each other to eliminate redundancies; and (3) these sequences were subjected to evaluation for miRNA precursor prediction properties using mirEval software¹⁵. These precursor sequences were used for BLASTx analysis for removing the protein-coding sequences and retained only the non-protein sequences.

Fig.1: Algorithm of potential *Jatropha curcus* miRNA gene search by identifying homolog's of previously known plant miRNAs

Result and Discussion:

We attempted to identify conserved miRNAs from *Jatropha curcus* using in-silico tools. There lies no microRNA. Sequences encoded range of proteins leading to no hairpin candidates and thus no potential miRNA genes. Algorithm limits up to a BLASTX search. Currently available genome sequence finds no individual conserved miRNAs.

Identification of miRNAs has remained a tedious job. We attempted to identify conserved miRNAs from *Jatropha curcus* using in-silico tools. Real time assays validate in-silico data, the same then adds to database. Reports find presence of potential miRNAs in the same¹³, but the same rebut when we went in-silico. A whole of 6 major plants were taken, searched across various databases. There lies no microRNA. Where lies the lacuna? Is it with the major databases? Or with the work? Or the standard international protocol does not stand good in this regard?

A form of gene regulation that uses small RNA molecules to bind to longer RNAs was first described over a

decade ago, but was thought to be of little significance in controlling cellular processes. No longer!

Based on the estimation that approx. 10,000 ESTs in plants contain a minimum of one miRNA, the total of 46,944 ESTs in *Jatropha* should contain a minimum of 4-5 miRNAs.

Among the many unanswered questions that surround micro-RNA function a central one is, what controls microRNA expression? Is there still another level of regulation that has been overlooked — another wave just beyond the horizon? What receptors might those miRNAs control?

The criteria for identification of miRNA precursors extend far beyond BLAST homology identification. Experimental evidence of precursor cleavage and actual identification of miRNAs by deep sequence or small RNA Northern is also warranted. For negative data, failure to detect miRNAs via deep sequencing or Northern blot analyses is also warranted.

Word is more confusion than a conclusion. The paper seeks broader scientific attention.

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Author contributions:

ND conceived the project. ND and SSR ran, analyzed, and interpreted the data. ND wrote the manuscript. RM supervised the work.

Competing financial interest:

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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